

Soil and Crop Management

Vertical distribution of soil solution NH_4^+ - N and grain yield of lowland rice with integrated N management

G.L. Sharma and B.S. Mahapatra,
Agronomy Department, G.B. Pant
University of Agriculture and Technology,
Pantnagar, Nainital 263145, U.P., India

In an INSFFER experiment on Jaya in lowland silty clay loam soil (pH 7.2, organic C 1.2%), grain yield was highest with 120 kg N/ha applied in integrated inorganic-organic approach

Grain yield of Jaya under integrated nitrogen management, Pantnagar, wet season, 1984-85.

Treatment ^a	N rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Check	0	3.4
USG	58	5.8
USG + fresh straw (29 + 29)	58	4.8
PU + <i>Azolla</i> (58 + 29)	87	6.7
PU + fresh straw (58 + 29)	87	6.2
USG + <i>Azolla</i> (58 + 29)	87	7.0
USG + fresh straw (58 + 29)	87	5.3
PU	120	7.3
USG + <i>Azolla</i> ^b (60 + 60)	120	8.0
CD (5%)		1.2

^a PU = prilled urea best split, USG = urea supergranules placed at 10-12 cm depth at 7 d after transplanting (DT), *Azolla* was incorporated.
^b 50% *Azolla* was incorporated and 50% inoculated at 7 DT.

(60 kg N/ ha through urea supergranules + 60 kg N/ha through *Azolla*) (see table). That better yield through an integrated approach is attributed to more N supplied to the soil solution NH_4^+ -N pool (see figure). Soil solution samples were taken anaerobically from piezometers installed at 10 and 20 cm depth of wet soil. □

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Soil solution ammonium-N (ppm)

Vertical distribution of soil solution ammonium-N under various N rates with integrated N management. FS = fresh straw.